

Face-selective regions in the human brain extend across the temporal lobe into anterior temporal cortex: FFA-1, FFA-2, aFG, and aTL-FA

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Abstract

Anterior temporal lobe regions of the ventral core-face system are proposed to play a critical role in face-identity processing, yet these areas are inconsistently localised in functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) studies. In the current study, we attempted to localise these regions using a targeted face-area localiser task where participants viewed images of faces or homogenous objects (watches). In conjunction, we employed a functional imaging sequence optimised for the ventral anterior temporal lobe (multi-echo fMRI). We observed face-selective responses (faces > watches) in the fusiform gyrus with peaks corresponding to the posterior and mid fusiform face area (FFA) i.e., FFA-1 and FFA-2. Strikingly, a third more anterior peak in the fusiform gyrus (aFG; $y = -30$) was also evident. We also identified a discrete face-selective cluster in the ventral anterior temporal lobe corresponding to the anterior temporal lobe face area (aTL-FA). These findings demonstrate face-selective regions that extend across the temporal lobe into anterior divisions, likely revealed by improved sensitivity of multi-echo fMRI. Together, the results support the view that the ventral core-face system extends beyond the posterior regions traditionally emphasised in models of face processing.

Keywords: face area localiser, face-identity, fusiform gyrus, anterior temporal lobe, multi-echo fMRI

Introduction

Recognising the identity of faces is a fundamental ability in humans and non-human primates (Bruce & Young, 1986; Chang & Tsao, 2017; Tsao et al., 2006; Valentine, 1991). In the human brain, this ability is supported by a ventral core-face system comprised of a set of spatially distributed regions which are selective for face processing (Axelrod & Yovel, 2013; Collins & Olson, 2014; Duchaine & Yovel, 2015; Gauthier, Tarr, et al., 2000; Haxby et al., 2000; Kanwisher et al., 1997; Rossion, 2014; Rossion et al., 2024). These face-selective regions reside in the occipital and temporal lobe, and may span the breadth of the temporal lobe into anterior divisions (Axelrod & Yovel, 2013; Gauthier, Tarr, et al., 2000; Kanwisher et al., 1997). However, owing to technical limitations, functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) investigations on the ventral core-face system have, thus far, largely been restricted to more posterior regions of the network.

The most posterior of these regions, located on the lateral surface of the occipital cortex, is the occipital face area (OFA) (Gauthier, Skudlarski, et al., 2000; Gauthier, Tarr, et al., 2000). This region is involved in the early perceptual analysis of faces, namely the analysis of individual face features (Liu et al., 2010; Pitcher et al., 2011; Pitcher et al., 2011 but see e.g., Ambrus et al., 2017; Rossion, 2008). Adjacent, in the fusiform gyrus in the inferior temporal lobe, lies the fusiform face area (FFA) (Kanwisher et al., 1997); arguably the most studied and consistently localised face-selective region in fMRI (Chen et al., 2023; Collins & Olson, 2014; Yovel et al., 2014). To date, the FFA is often regarded as a single homogenous region. However, growing evidence suggests that, at least in the typically developed brain, the FFA may have two subdivisions – FFA-1/pFus-faces in the posterior fusiform gyrus and a patch which lies more anterior in the middle fusiform gyrus, referred to as FFA-2/mFus-faces (Chen et al., 2023; Duchaine & Yovel, 2015; Engell & McCarthy, 2013; Grill-Spector et al., 2017; Pinsk et al., 2009; Weiner & Grill-Spector, 2010, 2012; Zhen et al., 2015). The FFA subdivisions are argued to be structurally distinct (Chen et al., 2023; Grill-Spector et al., 2017). Differences in their cytoarchitecture posits that they may also be engaged in different computations supporting face processing (Chen et al., 2023; Grill-Spector et al., 2017). Both regions are adjacent (see Table 1 for summary of peak voxel locations for FFA-1 and FFA-2). They can sometimes overlap and show no clear delineation (Chen et al., 2023), forming one cluster spanning from the posterior to middle fusiform gyrus (Zhen et al., 2015).

More anterior along the ventral network lies the anterior temporal lobe face area (aTL-FA) (Axelrod & Yovel, 2013; Collins & Olson, 2014; Pinsk et al., 2009; Rajimehr et al., 2009). The aTL-FA has been proposed as the potential pinnacle of the core-face system, serving as an interface for face-identity perception and face memory (Collins & Olson, 2014). When observed, aTL-FA face-selective responses are typically located in the anterior temporal fusiform gyrus, and, in some cases, adjacently within the anterior inferior temporal gyrus (Table 1). Compared to the well-studied FFA, fMRI studies on the aTL-FA are limited. The aTL-FA is notoriously difficult to localise as inferior regions of the anterior temporal lobe suffer severe signal drop out in standard fMRI (Axelrod &

Yovel, 2013; Devlin et al., 2000; Halai et al., 2014, 2015). Consequently, functional face-selective responses in this region are often poor (Axelrod & Yovel, 2013; Pinsk et al., 2009; Rajimehr et al., 2009; Tsao et al., 2008) and observed in as few as one half of participants or lower (Pinsk et al., 2009; Tsao et al., 2008). These poor responses are likely driven by the region’s anatomical location, which sits close to the ear canal. The difference in the magnetic susceptibility properties of air and brain tissue at this location leads to rapid signal dephasing, resulting in signal loss in standard single-echo echo planar imaging, one of the most extensively used sequences in fMRI research. As a result, the aTL-FA is not included in all functional neuroanatomical models of face processing (Grill-Spector et al., 2017; but see Duchaine & Yovel, 2015), limiting our understanding of a region likely crucial for face-identity recognition since lesions in this area lead to face-identity recognition deficits (Gainotti, 2013, 2018, 2025). Notably, positron emission tomography (PET) and electrophysiological studies suggest a further potential face processing region(s) nested between FFA-2 and the aTL-FA (Jonas et al., 2015; Rossion et al., 2001; Rossion et al., 2024). However, the region(s) is largely undocumented in fMRI (Rossion et al., 2012, 2024).

Table 1. Overview of the location (mean peak voxel MNI co-ordinates) for functionally localised (faces > visual control stimuli) subdivisions of the fusiform face area (FFA-1, FFA-2) and the anterior temporal lobe face area (aTL-FA) from existing fMRI studies.

Reference	Contrast	Right Hemisphere			Left Hemisphere		
		x	y	z	x	y	z
FFA-1/FFA-2							
Pinsk et al. (2009)	Faces > Objects	44/45	-61/-45	-14/-17	-40/-42	-60/-48	-13/-16
Weiner & Grill-Spector (2013)	Reported as 'face-selective'	38/39	-66/-50	-16/-18	-36/-39	-69/-53	-15/-18
McGugin et al. (2015)	Faces > Butterflies (ROI analysis)	44/44	-63/-41	-25/-27	-42/-43	-64/-43	-24/-26
Elbich & Scherf (2017)	[Famous + Novel Faces] > [Objects + Navigation]	41/41	-47/-39	-20/-22	-41/-41	-47/-34	-19/-22
McGugin et al. (2018)	Faces > Objects	41/41	-64/-46	-18/-22	-44/-43	-65/-46	-18/-22
Foster et al. (2021)	Faces > Objects + Scenes	42/42	-63/-44	-16/-19	-40/-41	-62/-43	-17/-21
aTL-FA							

Pinsk et al. (2009)	Faces > Objects	42	-2	-39	-38	-17*	-30
Nasr & Tootell (2012)	Faces > Places	34	-8	-36			
Axelrod & Yovel (2013)	Faces > Tables	34	-10	-39	-34	-11	-35
Avidan et al. (2014)	Faces > Buildings	34	-2	-42	-34	-4	-34
Yang et al. (2016)	Faces > Objects (dynamic stimuli)	44	1	-37	-40	1	-41
Foster et al. (2021)	Faces > Objects + Scenes	34	-5	-38	-35	-8	-34
Blank et al. (2023)	Faces > Scenes (masked with right temporal fusiform cortex, anterior division)	39	-18*	-32			
Garlichs & Blank (2024)	Faces > Scenes	34	-8	-38	-40	-20*	-38

All co-ordinates are reported in MNI space. For each axis (x, y, z) the co-ordinate for FFA-1 is listed first, followed by FFA-2 i.e., FFA-1/FFA-2. Talairach co-ordinates, when reported in the original publication, were converted to MNI space using the Matlab function `tal2icbm_spm.m` by Lancaster et al. (2007), rounded to the nearest whole number. Note that in some studies FFA-1 is synonymously referred to as pFus-faces or pFus; FFA-2 is referred to as mFus-faces or mFus. The anterior temporal lobe face area (aTL-FA) is also referred to as the face-sensitive aTL, ATL face area, ATFA, fATL, Ant. Temp., aIT, or AT. *In these publications, the y co-ordinate for the face-selective aTL-FA is relatively posterior; however, the co-ordinates remain within the anterior division of the temporal fusiform cortex, as defined by the probabilistic Harvard-Oxford Cortical Structural Atlas unthresholded maps.

A handful of fMRI studies on face processing have tried to reduce signal loss in the aTL and nearby regions by collecting images in coronal slice orientation (Axelrod & Yovel, 2013, 2015); an orientation that can reduce susceptibility artefacts (Axelrod & Yovel, 2013; O'Doherty et al., 2001). In conjunction with coronal slice acquisition, presenting an increased number of visual stimuli blocks (images of faces versus objects) has also been examined as a potential solution for boosting the detection of face-selective responses in the aTL (Axelrod & Yovel, 2013; Rajimehr et al., 2009). Signal loss can also be reduced in fMRI using an imaging sequence which employs *multiple* echoes; a technique called multi-echo echo planar imaging (ME-EPI) or multi-echo fMRI (Kundu et al., 2017; Poser et al., 2006; Poser & Norris, 2009). The basis of multi-echo fMRI is that the effective transverse relaxation time $T2^*$, which corresponds to the optimal echo time (TE) for fMRI, varies across brain regions. Therefore, an EPI image acquired at the shortest TE, when signal has not yet decayed significantly, is more sensitive to brain regions with short $T2^*$ values or strong susceptibility artifacts, such as the ventral anterior temporal lobe. EPI images acquired subsequently at longer TEs are more sensitive to less problematic brain regions. One common approach for processing multi-echo images, consists of combining the

weighted signals of the individual echoes into a single hybrid time series, thereby improving functional sensitivity for all brain regions (Poser et al., 2006). To the best of our knowledge, multi-echo fMRI has not been used to systematically examine face-selective responses in the ventral core-face system in the typically developed brain using classic localiser designs. One recent study used an intense fMRI protocol (five runs of 8-13 minutes each) and included personally familiar faces and diverse object stimuli and scenes to delineate anterior temporal lobe face regions using multi-echo fMRI (Deen et al., 2024). An open question is whether anterior temporal lobe face regions can be localised with fewer resources (e.g., shorter protocols) and greater specificity using localiser contrasts that minimise semantic processing and include homogenous control stimuli.

Here, we examined face-selective responses in the ventral core-face system, using a multi-echo sequence with two echoes, as participants viewed images of unfamiliar faces and objects presented in separate blocks i.e., a face area localiser task. Faces are a stimulus class that involve within category discrimination of highly homogeneous stimuli. Therefore, our control object stimuli were also taken from one object category only i.e., images of watches. This approach avoids the bias of larger variability (e.g., in shape or texture when images are drawn from multiple object categories or categories with different visual appearance such as scenes) in the object, compared to the face condition; allowing us to identify in a controlled manner regions which are *selective* for faces (Gauthier et al., 1999; Gauthier, Skudlarski, et al., 2000; Rossion et al., 2012). Participants completed two functional runs (each 8 minutes) of the face area localiser task. We had two primary pre-registered hypotheses (see <https://osf.io/9cuk8> for pre-registration). Firstly, using our face area localiser paradigm, acquired with the optimised multi-echo fMRI sequence, we expected to observe face-selective responses in *all* regions of the core-face system - OFA, FFA, *and* the problematic aTL-FA. If successful, this would provide a mapping of the entire ventral core-face system in the human brain. Secondly, we expected, in line with recent studies, that the FFA may contain two spatially distinct subdivisions i.e., FFA-1 and FFA-2. In an additional secondary pre-registered hypothesis, we also examined if an increased block number of visual stimuli (i.e., functional runs) may facilitate the detection of aTL-FA responses.

Materials and Methods

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee at Technische Universität Dresden (EK260052019). It was conducted at the Neuroimaging Center of the Technische Universität Dresden. All participants gave their written informed consent prior to participation and were reimbursed for their time.

Participants

Thirty-four typically developed German speaking adults (21 = female; $M_{age} = 28.2$ years, $SD = 6.6$ years) were included in the study. This sample size is on par with previous examinations of the FFA using similar visual conditions (Rossion et al., 2012). The

estimated minimum required sample size to detect FFA responses, faces versus within category objects (i.e., cars see Rossion et al., 2012), is $N = 20$. This N was calculated using previous effect size estimates for the FFA (faces v. cars, $t = 7.34$, $N = 40$; Rossion et al., 2012) in GPower 3.1 (Faul et al., 2007) with the following parameters: one-tailed, α error probability = 0.001, power = 0.90. Although the aTL-FA may show comparably lower responses (t values), the current sample size is threefold some previous attempts to localise the region (i.e., $N = 10$; Axelrod & Yovel, 2013).

All thirty-four participants were right-handed as measured by the Edinburgh Handedness Inventory Short Form (Oldfield, 1971; Veale, 2014) and all reported normal or corrected-to-normal vision. Normal visual acuity was also confirmed onsite using the Snellen Chart (Snellen, 1868), measured at a standard distance of 2.8m from the chart display. The test was administered separately for both eyes and corrective lenses were worn during the behavioural and MRI testing sessions for participants with a corrective prescription. As part of the study inclusion process, all participants completed the German-translated versions of the Autism Quotient (AQ) (Baron-Cohen et al., 2001; see Freitag et al., 2007 for translation) and the Prosopagnosia Index 20 (PI20) (Shah et al., 2015) to screen for potential autistic and developmental prosopagnosia traits, both of which can impact face processing. This PI20 was translated in-house. We refer to this German (Deutsch) version as the PI20-D, and it can be downloaded at <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/EQ5MZ>. Additionally, participants completed the Cambridge Face Memory Test – Australian (CFMT-Australian) as an objective measure of face-identity recognition performance (McKone et al., 2011). The CFMT-Australian is identical in design to the original CFMT (Duchaine & Nakayama, 2006) but uses face images that more reliably match the ethnicity of the current study population. All participants scored within the typical range on the AQ (i.e., <32 ; Baron-Cohen et al., 2001), the PI20-D (i.e., ≤ 64 of 100; Shah et al., 2015), and the CFMT-Australian (i.e., within 2 standard deviations of the published normative data; McKone et al., 2011). See Table 2 for mean AQ, PI20-D, and CFMT-Australian scores. Two additional pilot participants (both female, right-handed, 25 and 33 years old, AQ <32 , PI20-D <64) completed the dual-echo acquisition alongside a standard single-echo protocol used at the neuroimaging centre. These data served as a feasibility check to verify adequate signal in the ventral anterior temporal lobe (see Supplements, ‘Dual-echo EPI sequence pilot’). These two participants were not included in the main analysed sample.

Table 2. Mean scores (with min. and max. observed range and standard deviations) for the behavioural tests required for study inclusion in the $N=34$ typically developed participants.

	Mean	Range	SD
AQ	16.94	6 - 28	5.47
PI20-D	35.62	25 - 56	7.90
CFMT-Australian*	59.06	44 - 68	6.60

*Published normative data: $M_{score} = 57.73$, $SD = 7.34$ for $N=75$ (McKone et al. 2011). Maximum score = 72. 34/34 participants completed the AQ and PI20-D, 32/34 completed the CFMT-Australian.

Stimuli

The stimuli consisted of 160 colour images of unfamiliar faces and 160 colour images of objects. The face stimuli were taken from the 10k US Adult Faces Database (Bainbridge et al., 2013). The face images from the database included a dark grey oval shaped mask which excluded the background, while revealing the face. All faces displayed a frontal or a maximum 45° profile view, with both eyes clearly visible. The object stimuli were images of watches. All watch images were manual (non-digital) wrist watches taken from the Caltech 101 dataset (Li et al., 2022), in addition to images of manual wrist watches obtained through Google search. All watch images displayed the face of the watch, including the internal watch hands, and the wrist strap. The watch images were manually edited with the open-source GNU image manipulation programme (GIMP; <https://www.gimp.org/>) to remove any background information and a dark grey background was added. All face and watch images were batch resized with GIMP to measure 316 pixels (height) x 258 pixels (width) and presented on a grey background onscreen. The screen resolution was 800 x 600 pixels. All stimuli were presented using Presentation (www.neurobs.com) software.

Experimental Procedure

During the face area localiser task (Figure 1), participants were presented with images of faces or watches in separate blocks. Each block contained 16 images (faces or watches) and lasted 16 s. Images within a block were presented for 800 ms, with a blank interstimulus interval (ISI) of 200 ms. 10 blocks were presented per image condition i.e., 10 blocks for faces (160 face images) and 10 blocks for objects (160 watch images). Images within a block were presented in a randomised order. 10 baseline blocks containing a white fixation cross were also shown. Each baseline block was 16 s in duration. All blocks were presented in a randomised order, with the exception that no two blocks of the same condition (faces, watches, baseline) could follow each other. We asked participants to attentively view the images and to press a button when they detected a change in image condition (e.g., watches-faces, watches-baseline). We chose this task, rather than e.g., an n-back task (Axelrod & Yovel, 2013), as we aimed to develop a face area localiser task that could be utilised in populations with difficulties in face processing i.e., developmental prosopagnosia.

In total, there were 30 blocks (10 blocks per condition) presented in a run. The duration of the run was circa 8 min (i.e., 16 s per block x 3 conditions x 10 blocks). We acquired two runs, so that the experiment lasted circa 16 minutes in total. The second run was a direct repetition of the first run (identical images, identical design), but the blocks were presented in a newly randomised order. We recorded participants' eye movements using an MRI-compatible CE-certified eye tracking system (Eyelink 1000 by SR Research Ltd). This allowed for online quality control and confirmed that participants

remained alert during the face area localiser task and viewed the images. The full eye tracking data were collected as part of the larger project to be reported elsewhere.

Figure 1. (A) Schematic illustration of the face area localiser experiment. Images of unfamiliar faces, watches, and a baseline fixation cross were shown in separate blocks. The blocks (16 s each) were presented in a randomised order, with the exception that no two blocks of the same condition could follow each other. Participants were instructed to attend to the images and to press a button when there was a change in image condition e.g., faces-watches, watches-baseline. The experiment lasted circa 16 min in total (8 min x 2 runs). (B) Sample images from the face and watch blocks. Each image was presented for 800 ms followed by a 200 ms blank screen interstimulus interval. The displayed face images are from the 49-face database (Bainbridge et al., 2013) and are representative of the images used in the main experiment. Exact face images from the main experiment are not shown due to copyright restrictions. Watch images are attribution free or creative common licensed (Joydeep; Nobunga123).

Image Acquisition

All functional and structural images (including pilot data) were acquired on a 3 Tesla MR scanner (Tim Trio, Siemens, Erlangen, Germany), equipped with a 32-channel receive head coil.

Functional MRI

Functional images were acquired using the CMRR multi-band gradient-echo EPI sequence (Moeller et al., 2010), which also offers multi-echo acquisitions. To address the susceptibility-related signal drop out in our target region, we chose a dual-echo protocol, hereafter referred to as dual-echo EPI/fMRI, with the following parameters: TE1 = 12.6 ms; TE2 = 33.6 ms; flip angle = 90 degrees; TR = 1.832 s; multi-band (SMS) acceleration factor = 2; GeneRalised Autocalibrating Partial Parallel Acquisition (GRAPPA) acceleration factor = 2; 60 slices whole brain coverage; 2 mm slice thickness with 0.5 mm interslice gap (2.5 mm spacing); in plane resolution 2.5 mm x 2.5 mm; bandwidth: 1966 Hz/pixel. The images were acquired with slices oriented relative to the anterior commissure – posterior commissure (AC-PC) plane, with an anterior tilt of approximately 15°. A total of 610 volumes (2 echo images per volume) were acquired across two runs (305 volumes per run) for the face area localiser task. At the beginning of each run, prior to task onset, 30 auxiliary volumes (2 echo images per volume) were acquired. These were used to calculate the weighting factors for the echo combination (see Data Analysis, Functional MRI). Geometric distortions were characterised by a B0 field map acquired once per participant. The map was calculated from a pair of 2D gradient echo images with different echo times (TE1/TE2 = 5.19 ms/7.65 ms).

Structural MRI

Structural images were acquired using a T1-weighted three-dimensional magnetisation-prepared rapid gradient echo (MP-RAGE) sequence (Mugler & Brookeman, 1990) (TR = 1.9 s; TE = 2.26 ms; TI = 900 ms; flip angle = 9 degrees; FOV = 256 mm × 224 mm, in-plane resolution = 1 x 1 mm²; 176 sagittal slices; slice thickness = 1mm).

Data Analysis

Behavioural

The dependent variable was accuracy in detecting a change in the image condition e.g., faces-watches, watches-baseline. We calculated percent correct performance for each participant, that is, the number of correctly identified image condition changes/total number of image condition changes*100. This was calculated for both run 1 and run 2. A paired *t*-test was conducted on accuracy scores for run 1 and run 2 to assess potential performance differences between runs.

Functional MRI

Echo-combination and pre-processing

We created a hybrid time series consisting of a weighted sum of the two echo time series using Statistical Parametric Mapping (SPM12, update 7219; www.fil.ion.ucl.ac.uk/spm) and an additional script, both implemented in MATLAB (version 9.3; MathWorks, MA, USA). In the first step, both echo time series (including their auxiliary volumes) were re-sliced using identical alignment parameters derived from the first echo's time series. The

auxiliary volumes of both echoes were then extracted and used to calculate temporal signal-to-noise (tSNR) maps for each echo, from which the weighting factor maps for the echo summation was obtained. The resulting hybrid time series were created independently for both runs, excluding auxiliary volumes for both.

We further pre-processed and analysed these functional hybrid data with SPM12 (update 7219; <https://www.fil.ion.ucl.ac.uk/spm>). We used standard spatial pre-processing procedures: images were realigned between (i.e., the first image from each run was realigned to the first image in run 1) and within functional runs and unwarped (based on the voxel displacement map calculated using the magnitude and phase image of the B0 field map), normalised to Montreal Neurological Institute (MNI) standard stereotactic space using the structural image (T1) of each participant, written to the original resolution of the functional data, and smoothed with an isotropic Gaussian filter of 4 mm at full width half maximum (FWHM). As per the pre-registration, this smoothing kernel size was chosen to facilitate identification of potential subregions of the FFA at the group level.

Anatomical masks

Grey matter mask: Segmented grey matter masks for each participant were created during pre-processing using the forward deformation field (y^*) generated during the spatial normalisation procedure to MNI space. The masks were resampled to the resolution of the functional data. A mean group grey matter mask was generated in Image Calculator in SPM12 using the single-subject grey matter masks. The mean group grey matter mask was smoothed to match the functional data (i.e., 4mm FWHM) and binarised (all voxels with a grey matter probability of 30% or more (i.e., >0.3) were included in the mask).

Ventral core-face system mask: An anatomical mask encompassing the ventral core-face system was defined based on probabilistic maps of the respective regions from the Harvard-Oxford Cortical Structural Atlas (Desikan et al., 2006), implemented in FSL (Smith et al., 2004). For both hemispheres, we extracted probabilistic maps for the following anatomical regions: lateral occipital cortex inferior division (inferior LOC), occipital fusiform gyrus (OFG), temporal occipital fusiform cortex (TOFC), temporal fusiform cortex posterior division (posterior TFC), temporal fusiform cortex anterior division (anterior TFC), and inferior temporal gyrus anterior division (anterior ITG). The maps were extracted unthresholded. We confirmed that the span of the extracted maps at this threshold encompassed the predicted functional locations of all potential ventral core-face regions: the OFA (Pitcher et al., 2011, 2023; Zhen et al., 2015), the FFA (including posterior and potentially more anterior divisions, Table 1) and the aTL-FA (Table 1). A higher threshold (30%) missed key peak voxel co-ordinates for FFA subregions. Due to the extraction threshold, there was inherent overlap between adjacent anatomical maps (see 'Statistical Inference' for details on anatomical labelling of peak responses). The extracted maps are displayed in Figure 2. The maps were binarised and

then combined using FSL. The combined map was resliced to match the functional data and then intersected with the mean group grey matter mask using FSL to produce a single comprehensive ventral core-face system mask that was restricted to meaningful grey matter voxels (Turner & Geyer, 2014); see Supplements Figure S2.

Figure 2. Visualisation of all regions included in the ventral core-face mask extracted from the Harvard-Oxford Cortical Structural Atlas displayed in sagittal (left of figure, right hemisphere) and coronal (right of figure) view. The masks are restricted to and displayed on the MNI template brain. The regions included, from posterior to anterior (left of figure), the bilateral: inferior division of the lateral occipital cortex (green colour), occipital fusiform gyrus (copper colour), temporal occipital fusiform cortex (red colour), temporal fusiform cortex posterior division (violet colour), and anterior divisions of the temporal fusiform cortex (dark blue colour, left and right of figure) and inferior temporal gyrus (cyan colour, left and right of figure). Each region is outlined in black. Overlap between the anatomical region maps is depicted with transitioning colours. Note the mask extends superiorly in the lateral occipital cortex, owing to the threshold adopted for the probabilistic maps.

Contrasts of Interest

Statistical parametric maps were generated in SPM12 by modelling the evoked hemodynamic response for the different image conditions (faces, watches) as boxcars convolved with a synthetic hemodynamic response function in the context of the general linear model (Friston et al., 2007). The baseline condition was implicitly modelled. Realignment parameters outputted during motion correction as part of the echo combination procedure were modelled as regressors of no interest (i.e., nuisance regressors) at the first level. The contrast of interest ‘faces > watches’ was computed at the single-subject level for both runs combined. To address our two primary hypotheses, these first-level contrasts of interest ‘faces > watches’ were taken to a group-level random-effects analysis which estimated the second-level *t*-statistic at each voxel. As per our pre-registration, we conducted two group analyses. The first analysis was restricted to the ventral core-face system. In this analysis the ventral core-face system mask was entered as an explicit mask during design specification. The second was a whole-brain analysis in which the mean grey matter group mask was entered as the explicit mask.

Whole-brain analysis results, including responses in regions outside the ventral core-face system, are reported in the Supplements in Table S1. For exploratory purposes, the contrast ‘faces > baseline’ was also computed at the single-subject level and taken to the group-level random-effects analysis in the same manner as outlined above.

In our secondary hypothesis, we investigated if the number of visual stimuli (i.e., face and watch condition blocks) may influence the detection of responses in the aTL-FA (Axelrod & Yovel, 2013; Rajimehr et al., 2009) i.e., that BOLD responses may increase (t values and/or cluster size) with increased block number (i.e., runs). To address this hypothesis, we computed the contrast ‘faces > watches’ separately for run 1 and run 2. Again, we brought these contrasts to a group-level random-effects analysis which estimated the second-level t -statistic at each voxel. To examine differences between runs, a paired t -test was conducted at the second level. These analyses were restricted to the ventral core-face system mask using the explicit masking procedure described above and as per the pre-registration are reported for aTL-FA responses only.

Statistical Inference

Group analyses results for face-selective responses (face > watches) are reported at two pre-registered statistical thresholds: $p < 0.001$ uncorrected - the threshold applied to localise the aTL-FA in prior studies (Axelrod & Yovel, 2013) and $p < 0.05$ family wise error (FWE) corrected - a more conservative threshold that may allow spatial separation of responses in the fusiform gyrus (Rossion et al., 2012). The exploratory analysis to examine signal in the aTL (and OFA) for the contrast ‘faces > baseline’ is reported at $p < 0.05$ family wise error (FWE) corrected only. All peak voxel response co-ordinates are reported in MNI standard stereotactic space. The anatomical label for each peak voxel within the ventral core-face system was determined using the extracted maps (unthresholded and binarised see ‘Ventral core-face system mask’) for each anatomical region. Specifically, if a peak fell within the map of a given core-face region (e.g., anterior TFC), it was assigned that region’s label. If a peak fell within overlapping anatomical maps, the label of the region with the highest probability of containing that voxel, according to the Harvard-Oxford Cortical Structural Atlas, was assigned. In some cases, a peak response straddled the boundary with adjacent anatomical regions outside the map. In these instances, we also report these adjacent regions for information purposes.

Results

Behavioural

The mean percent correct for detecting a change in image category, for both face area localiser runs, was 95.8 % ($SD = 2.7$ %). There was no difference between the accuracy scores for run 1 ($M_{\% \text{ correct}} = 95.9$ %, $SD = 2.6$ %) and run 2 ($M_{\% \text{ correct}} = 95.7$ %, $SD = 3.8$ %) ($t(33) = 0.30$, $p = 0.76$, 95% CI [-1.51, 1.11]).

Functional MRI

Ventral core-face mask: Faces > watches (combined runs)

The fusiform face area contains multiple face-selective peaks

At $p < 0.05$ FWE corrected, the group analysis restricted to the ventral core-face mask, revealed a face-selective cluster in the temporal occipital fusiform cortex i.e., fusiform gyrus (right hemisphere) for the contrast ‘faces > watches’. In line with our hypothesis, this cluster contained two distinct peaks (Table 3; Figure 4). The difference in the y axis co-ordinates is suggestive of 2 FFA sub-regions corresponding to a posterior (FFA-1 at $y = -50$) and anterior FFA (FFA-2 at $y = -42$). The posterior peak is more anterior to previous reports, which often locate FFA-1 1-1.5 cm posterior to FFA-2 (see Table 1). However, similar observations of a less pronounced spatial distinction between the sub-regions have also been observed (Elbich & Scherf, 2017; Table 1). In terms of the left hemisphere, parallel responses were observed at $p < 0.001$ uncorrected only. These followed a similar pattern to the dominant right hemisphere – with a posterior FFA peak evident at -55 on the y axis and an anterior at $y = -42$ (Table 3).

Figure 4. Face-selective responses in the temporal occipital fusiform cortex localised using the faces > watches contrast in the right hemisphere. Crosshairs indicate the peak voxel location for each of the two separate peaks identified (displayed at t threshold = 3.36). The colour bar represents t values. (A) FFA-1: $x = 43$, $y = -50$, $z = -22$. (B) FFA-2: $x = 43$, $y = -42$, $z = -26$. Responses are overlaid on a mean structural MNI152 T1 weighted image (sagittal and coronal views, right hemisphere). FFA = fusiform face area.

Table 3. Overview of the face-selective responses observed in the ventral core-face system for the contrast ‘faces > watches’ for both runs combined.

Faces > watches (combined runs)												
Right hemisphere						Left Hemisphere						
x	y	z	T	Z	Size (mm ³)	x	y	z	T	Z	Size (mm ³)	

p < 0.05 (FWE corrected)												
FFA-1 (TOFC)	43	-50	-22	6.85	5.37	763						
FFA-2 (TOFC)	43	-42	-26	8.78	6.26							
LOC	56	-65	18	5.56	4.64	50						
p < 0.001 (uncorrected)												
FFA-1 (TOFC)	43	-50	-22	6.85	5.37	2588	-45	-55	-22	3.84	3.47	850
FFA-2 (TOFC)	43	-42	-26	8.78	6.26		-42	-42	-22	4.74	4.11	
aFG (post. TFC/ITG)	43	-30	-16	4.48	3.93		-42	-35	-18	3.85	3.47	
post. TFC/ITG	46	-15	-30	3.61	3.29	25						
aTL-FA (ant. TFC)	31	-5	-36	3.84	3.46	63						
LOC	56	-65	18	5.56	4.64	1688	-52	-70	22	4.93	4.23	813
	46	-60	22	4.70	4.08		-52	-72	14	4.52	3.96	

FFA = fusiform face area; aFG = anterior fusiform gyrus; aTL-FA = anterior temporal lobe face area; post. = posterior; ant = anterior; TOFC = Temporal occipital fusiform cortex; TFC = Temporal fusiform cortex; ITG = inferior temporal gyrus; LOC = lateral occipital cortex. Note we report functional and anatomical labels in this table. The functional regions could be in different anatomical maps created from the Harvard-Oxford Cortical Structural Atlas. See the main text for details on anatomical map creation and peak co-ordinate anatomical labelling.

Face-selective responses are evident in anterior regions of the core-face system

Notably, and in line with our hypothesis, face-selective responses in the ventral anterior temporal lobe were also evident i.e., the aTL-FA was localised in the anterior division of the temporal fusiform cortex ($y = -5$; Table 3; Figure 5). These responses were detected at a threshold of $p < 0.001$ (uncorrected) and align with previous published group co-ordinates for the region at this threshold (e.g., Axelrod & Yovel, 2013; see Table 1).

At the same threshold, a 3rd peak was evident in the cluster that housed FFA-1 and FFA-2. This 3rd peak was circa 8 mm anterior to FFA-2 (on y axis) and localised in both hemispheres (see Table 3 and Figure 5) in the posterior temporal fusiform cortex (probability 10%), bordering with the posterior division of the inferior temporal gyrus (probability 20%). In the right hemisphere, this 3rd peak was located at $x = 43$, $y = -30$, $z = -16$. These co-ordinates, particularly on the y-axis, align well with previously reported co-ordinates for face-related sensitivity in the inferotemporal cortex/anterior fusiform gyrus (aFG/antFG)(Jonas et al., 2015; Jonas et al., 2016; Rossion et al., 2001). For example, Rossion et al. (2001) reported responses at $x = 42$, $y = -28$, $z = -24$ (Talairach co-ordinates). The aFG has been previously reported in the context of studies using PET (Rossion et al., 2001) or electrophysiological methodologies (Jonas et al., 2015).

Figure 5. Anterior face-selective responses for the contrast faces > watches. (A) Responses in the anterior division of the temporal fusiform cortex i.e., the anterior temporal lobe face area (aTL-FA). Responses are shown at the same peak voxel location (indicated via crosshairs: at $x = 31$, $y = -5$, $z = -36$, displayed at t threshold = 2.4) in sagittal (left) and coronal (right) view in the right hemisphere. (B) Responses in the face-selective cluster spanning the temporal occipital fusiform/posterior temporal fusiform cortex (displayed at t threshold = 3.36). Crosshairs indicate the peak voxel location for the third face-selective peak identified in this cluster, corresponding approximately on the y axis to previous reports for the anterior fusiform gyrus (aFG). The colour bar represents t values.

In the right hemisphere, an additional small (25 mm^3) but spatially distinct face-selective cluster, separated by $\sim 1.5\text{cm}$ along the posterior-anterior axis from the aFG peak, was also detected in the ventral temporal cortex, bordering the inferior temporal gyrus (posterior division) and temporal fusiform cortex ($y = -15$). See Table 3 for all peak co-ordinates, cluster size, and corresponding statistics.

Signal in the ventral anterior temporal lobe: end of the 'black box'

As a complimentary analysis, we also examined responses in the anterior temporal lobe for the contrast 'faces > baseline' for both runs combined. Although non-face-selective, this contrast provides important insight into the magnitude of signal in this problematic region which often presents as a 'black box' in the human brain in standard functional neuroimaging. For this contrast, robust ($t = 7.97$, cluster size 213 mm^3 , Supplements Table S2) peak responses were observed in the anterior division of the temporal fusiform cortex at $x = 28$, $y = -5$, $z = 36$ at a conservative threshold of $p < 0.05$ FWE corrected.

No face-selective responses in the inferior occipital gyrus

Contrary to our predictions, we did not observe face-selective responses (faces > watches) in the inferior occipital gyrus, an anatomical region encompassing the typical location of the occipital face area (OFA), at either statistical threshold ($p < 0.05$ FWE corrected, $p < 0.001$ uncorrected). Notably, this was not driven by signal drop out in the region. An exploratory analysis of the contrast 'faces > baseline' confirmed robust bilateral responses within the inferior division of the lateral occipital cortex in the right

($x = 38, y = -75, z = -16$) and left ($x = -47, y = -77, z = 2$) hemisphere ($p < 0.05$ FWE corrected, see Supplements Figure S3; Table S2 for statistics), demonstrating measurable visually evoked responses. These non-face-selective peaks were in line with the predicted location of the OFA (Pitcher et al., 2011). Face-selective responses were evident more superiorly in the LOC (Table 3).

Ventral core-face mask: Faces > watches (run 1, run 2)

The detectability of face-selective responses in the ventral anterior temporal lobe may be influenced by run number

Previous reports suggest that increasing the number of visual stimulus blocks can enhance detection of aTL-FA responses - Axelrod & Yovel (2013) found larger aTL-FA responses (extent in mm^3) when modelling 30 blocks (3 runs) compared to 20 (2 runs) or 10 (1 run). Based on this, we examined aTL-FA responses for run 1 alone, using a smaller number of blocks – 10 per visual condition. Unlike the combined run analysis, we found no face-selective responses in the ventral anterior temporal lobe for the contrast ‘faces > watches’ at the $p < 0.001$ uncorrected threshold indicating that one run of circa 8 minutes might not be sufficient. For exploratory purposes, we next applied a more lenient threshold ($p < 0.01$ uncorrected), consistent with previous studies examining the aTL (Rajimehr et al., 2009). At this threshold, run 1 revealed peak face-selective responses at $x = 31, y = -5, z = -34$ ($t = 2.71$, cluster size 25mm^3).

Notably, as per the current study, Axelrod & Yovel (2013) repeated the blocks across runs i.e., the same images were presented again to participants. Therefore, it is unclear whether previous enhanced aTL-FA responses observed with increased block number are driven by increased power (from stimulus number), or by repeated exposure to the visual stimuli and the increased responses to familiar faces in aTL-FA (Deen et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2016). Therefore, we explicitly examined responses separately for run 2. For run 2, face-selective responses were observed for the aTL-FA at $x = 31, y = -5, z = -36$ ($t = 3.88, p < 0.001$ uncorrected), in line with the combined run analysis (see Table 3 for combined run results). At the more lenient threshold ($p < 0.01$ uncorrected), the cluster size of this aTL-FA region for run 2 was 325mm^3 . However, a paired t -test contrasting face-selective responses between runs (run 2 > run 1), revealed no significant response differences, even at a lenient statistical threshold ($p < 0.01$ uncorrected), demonstrating no major detectable differences in aTL-FA responses between the two runs.

Discussion

The present study has three central findings. First, we replicated that the fusiform face area contains sub regions corresponding to the posterior (FFA-1) and more anterior (FFA-2) FFA and demonstrated that these peaks are detectable at the group level with a spatial smoothing of 4 mm FWHM. Second, we localised the aTL-FA in the ventral anterior temporal lobe, detectable with two functional runs (2 x 8 minutes) of visual stimulation.

Additional peaks were also observed between the aTL-FA and the FFA-2 peak, i.e., the aFG. This highlights that the ventral core-face system may be organised along a posterior-to-anterior axis, extending from posterior face-selective regions into the anterior temporal lobe (Axelrod & Yovel, 2013; Rossion et al., 2024) rather than being confined to posterior fusiform cortex (Grill-Spector et al., 2017). Third, the use of imaging methods optimised for imaging of the problematic ventral aTL (dual-echo fMRI) enabled localisation of these regions, which have been overlooked and under-detected in prior models of face-identity processing in the human brain (Grill-Spector et al., 2017).

Face-selective responses in the fusiform gyrus

We identified two face-selective peaks in the fusiform gyrus, consistent with the location of FFA-1 and FFA-2. Notably, these face-selective responses were part of a continuous cluster; although spatially distinct by peak co-ordinates, they could not be delineated as separate clusters. This is in line with previous observations, which have shown that the topographical organisation of the FFAs can present as continuous, separate, or less commonly, as a single detectable region (Chen et al., 2023; Zhen et al., 2015). Differences in the cytoarchitecture between FFA subregions suggests that they are likely engaged in different computations supporting face processing (Chen et al., 2023; Grill-Spector et al., 2017). Emerging evidence demonstrates that both regions are implicated in holistic face processing (Foster et al., 2021; Pinsk et al., 2009; Poltoratski et al., 2021). However, perturbation of FFA-1 ($y = -45$), rather than more anterior fusiform areas, produces distortions in the perceived appearance of faces (particularly facial features, Table S9, Schrouff et al. (2020)), suggesting that this more posterior FFA may be particularly sensitive to perceptual face processing (Schrouff et al., 2020). Notably, the face-selectivity of both regions is more similar in monozygotic than dizygotic twins, suggesting that genetic factors may contribute to their functional organisation (Chen et al., 2023). Potentially, this functional organisation could have behavioural consequences. For example, Wilmer et al. (2010) observed that monozygotic twins (i.e. developed from one fertilized oocyte) show highly correlated face-identity recognition performance. This correlation was more than double that observed for dizygotic twins, raised in the same environment (correlation 0.70 versus 0.29, respectively).

The anterior temporal lobe face area – a core-face region

Functional neuroanatomical models of face-identity processing in the human brain are divided on the role of anterior temporal regions. Historically, the aTL has been regarded as a component of the ‘extended system’ (Gobbini & Haxby, 2007; Haxby et al., 2000), a hub for *multimodal* semantic processing. Other models emphasise the role of the aTL-FA in visual face-identity processing (Collins & Olson, 2014; Duchaine & Yovel, 2015). Such views highlight the region’s role in coding face-identity information across image transformations (Duchaine & Yovel, 2015), demonstrating that this functional region of the aTL may represent identity at a more abstract level than posterior core-face regions

(Guntupalli et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2016). Such views conceive the aTL-FA as the potential pinnacle of the core-face system (Collins & Olson, 2014).

In contrast, Grill-Spector et al. (2017) has focused such models on posterior regions of the core-face system only (OFA, FFAs). They do not conceive anterior face-sensitive regions as part of the core-face system “as they are not just driven by visual stimulation and are more elusive to identify because of lower signals and susceptibility artifacts in fMRI”. Although the authors highlight methodological challenges, their statement also implies that aTL face responses reflect multimodal semantic or affective processing, rather than visual face processing (Rossion and colleagues (2024) reach a similar interpretation of Grill-Spector et al.’s statement). Importantly, we show in the current study that responses in the aTL-FA *are driven by visual stimulation*. The presented face images were unfamiliar to participants. Moreover, responses to these images were contrasted against a tightly controlled homogenous visual stimulus category. This suggests that aTL-FA responses are visually face-selective and not dependent on general semantic mechanisms. Indeed, lesion studies demonstrate that damage to specific regions of the aTL can produce selective recognition deficits in face-identity processing, while leaving other modalities intact (e.g., intact voice-identity recognition and vice versa)(Gainotti, 2025; Luzzi et al., 2018). However, (right) temporal pole lesions can produce multimodal recognition deficits affecting both face and voice representations at the potential locus of conversion of these multimodal identity streams (Gainotti, 2025) suggesting a tight packing of multimodal and face-selective responses in this region.

Notably, recent work by Deen et al. (2024), also using multi-echo fMRI (three echoes), demonstrated similar visually driven responses in the aTL. The authors observed responses in the perirhinal cortex, largely localised to the anterior collateral sulcus, for faces as a visual category (videos of unfamiliar faces > videos of objects and scenes). Additionally, in a second contrast, the perirhinal cortex appeared to be relatively insensitive to face familiarity (familiar > unfamiliar), at least in the right hemisphere. This was in marked contrast to the familiarity driven responses observed in the temporal pole. The authors noted that the perirhinal cortex responses were broadly consistent in anatomical location with the previously reported aTL face patch (see Table 1) and suggested this region be more precisely labelled the ‘PR face area’ (PR = perirhinal cortex).

In the present study, face-selective responses within the ventral aTL (detected following 4mm spatial smoothing) were localised to the anterior division of the temporal fusiform cortex. Examination of the peak co-ordinates using the Jülich-Brain cytoarchitectonic atlas (Human Brain Project, 2024; Amunts & Zilles, 2015; Eickhoff et al., 2005) indicated that these responses fell predominantly within unlabelled temporal-to-parietal “GapMap” territory, with only partial overlap with entorhinal cortex (28%).

Accordingly, Deen et al.’s proposed relabelling of *all* historical aTL face patches as PR may be premature. While face-selective responses within the PR are consistent with

proposals, by e.g., Collins & Olson (2014), that a subpopulation of neurons in PR may be optimally tuned for faces, anterior temporal face responses likely extend beyond a single cytoarchitecture. It is conceivable that the spatial distinction of responses in aTL regions (perirhinal cortex vs. temporal isocortex) may reflect different neural processes (Jonas et al., 2016).

Notably, in the current study, robust aTL-FA responses were observed in the combined run analysis (2 x 8 minutes). This likely reflects the increased statistical power afforded by the greater number of stimulus blocks, a pattern also noted by Axelrod & Yovel (2013). No significant differences were evident in aTL-FA responses between the runs. Importantly, this demonstrates that the region can be detected using unfamiliar faces and that a longer protocol (i.e., 2 x 8 minutes) improves detection.

Additional anterior face-selective responses

Strikingly, we detected a face-selective peak centered at $y = -30$. Along the anterior-posterior axis, this co-ordinate falls within the range of previously reported anterior fusiform face-sensitivity. The y co-ordinate aligns with the anterior fusiform gyrus (aFG) and is within limits of the probabilistic mapping of the anterior FFA (Jonas et al., 2015; Rossion et al., 2001; Rossion et al., 2024; Zhen et al., 2015). Rossion et al. (2024) collectively defined face-sensitive areas in this vicinity anatomically as the aFG+. The aFG+ encompasses the anterior fusiform gyrus together with the anterior collateral sulcus and anterior occipito-temporal sulcus. Notably, this area falls within the anterior ventral temporal imaging “gap” zone as its position between FFA-2 and the aTL-FA (estimated to lie between circa. -30 to -10 on the y axis, Talairach; see Figure 5B in Rossion et al., 2024) makes it highly susceptible to signal drop-out in conventional fMRI (Chen et al., 2023; Rossion et al., 2024). The present findings suggest that the peak at $y = -30$ reflects a posterior portion of this aFG+ territory, that is detectable with dual-echo fMRI acquisition. In addition, we also observed an additional small, but spatially distinct, face-selective peak at -15 on the y axis. This co-ordinate may align with the anterior extent of the aFG+.

Direct electrical stimulation of the posterior part of the aFG+ (circa -21 to -30 on the y -axis, Talairach) results in severely impaired face-identity recognition i.e., transient prosopagnosia (Jonas et al., 2015; Rossion et al., 2024; Volfart et al., 2022). Visually presented familiar faces are perceived as strangers “I asked to myself, who is this person?” - patient CD (Jonas et al., 2015). Importantly, during such direct stimulation, face perception appears unaffected, as does the visual recognition of nonface objects, and the identification of familiarity from visually presented names (Jonas et al., 2015; Volfart et al., 2022). These observations suggest that the aFG+ appears *critical* for successful visual face-identity recognition. The current findings demonstrate that dual-echo (multi-echo) fMRI can help reveal potential multiple face-selective areas along the posterior-anterior axis; areas that have previously been overlooked, and their potential functional properties underappreciated, due to methodological limitations.

The occipital face area

We did not localise the occipital face area in the current study. Previous fMRI studies have demonstrated considerable variation in the location of the OFA at both the group and individual level, and that its detectability may be dependent on the statistical threshold applied (Pitcher et al., 2011; Rossion et al., 2012). Even at a lenient threshold, we did not identify face-selective responses in the vicinity of the lateral occipital gyrus. Potentially, the lack of OFA responses may relate to methodological factors from the chosen paradigm. We used a homogenous visual control category, i.e., watches, and a low-demand task that did not require explicit discrimination of the presented face stimuli. This task was chosen to minimise task-difficulty effects (e.g., n-back tasks) that can increase attention to faces and modulate the extent of face-selective responses, thereby allowing the localiser to be used in populations with face-identity processing difficulties. Notably, Haist et al. (2010), using a similar task (passive viewing) and control stimuli (watches), also observed that the OFA responded similarly to faces and watches, leading the authors to conclude that the region may be sensitive to general stimulus homogeneity, at least during spontaneous (rather than directed) processing. Additionally, it is also possible that inter-individual variability in the location and extent of the OFA (Ambrus et al., 2017; McGugin et al., 2023; Pitcher et al., 2011) may have reduced the ability to detect this functional region at the group level.

Adopting multi-echo fMRI

In the current study, we acquired two echoes (shorter and longer TE). Realistic tSNR values were obtained by recording auxiliary volumes, and the echoes were combined using a voxel-wise tSNR weighting approach. Compared to simple averaging of the echoes, this approach allows the echo with the most reliable signal in each voxel to contribute more strongly to the combined time series (Poser et al., 2006). This approach improves BOLD contrast sensitivity in regions with short T2* and susceptibility artefacts. Such optimisation is particularly relevant for the ventral anterior temporal lobe, an area which is notoriously difficult to image with standard single-echo fMRI.

Alternative multi-echo processing methods also exist, including TE-dependent independent component analysis pipelines (e.g., tedana; Kundu et al., 2012; Prantik Kundu et al., 2017). These exploit the TE-dependence of the BOLD signal to classify and remove non-neural components of the signal (e.g., motion, physiological variance). Such approaches typically require that three or more echoes are acquired to accurately model TE-dependency. However, in regions such as the ventral aTL, which have very short T2* values, the signal of the third or fourth echo is often greatly attenuated and no longer contributes to the desired effect. Circumventing this with multi-echo protocols with even shorter inter-echo times comes at the price of higher Grappa acceleration factors, which are known to further reduce tSNR values. The dual-echo approach could therefore be a good compromise between the more sophisticated acquisition methods and the necessary robustness in regions with strong susceptibility artefacts.

Conclusion

The current study highlights the distributed array of face-selective areas within the inferior temporal lobe, including anterior regions that are challenging to detect with conventional fMRI. Combining multi-echo fMRI (here dual-echo) with tailored behavioural paradigms therefore offers a potential powerful approach for localising discrete face-selective regions, particularly in the ventral aTL. This approach offers a practical tool for future investigations of face processing in both typical development and developmental prosopagnosia. More broadly, continued advancements in functional imaging methods will likely play a central role in refining our understanding of the anatomical and functional landscape of anterior face regions, including the aFG+, which Rossion et al. (2024) poignantly described as the “the ghost in the cortical machine”.

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References

- Ambrus, G. G., Dotzer, M., Schweinberger, S. R., & Kovács, G. (2017). The occipital face area is causally involved in the formation of identity-specific face representations. *Brain Structure & Function*, *222*, 4271–4282. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00429-017-1467-2>
- Amunts, K., & Zilles, K. (2015). Primer Architectonic Mapping of the Human Brain beyond Brodmann. *Neuron*, *88*(6), 1086–1107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2015.12.001>
- Avidan, G., Tanzer, M., Hady-Bouziane, F., Liu, N., Ungerleider, L. G., & Behrmann, M. (2014). Selective dissociation between core and extended regions of the face processing network in congenital prosopagnosia. *Cerebral Cortex*, *24*(6), 1565–1578. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bht007>
- Axelrod, V., & Yovel, G. (2013). The challenge of localizing the anterior temporal face area: A possible solution. *NeuroImage*, *81*, 371–380.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2013.05.015>

- Axelrod, V., & Yovel, G. (2015). Successful decoding of famous faces in the fusiform face area. *PLoS ONE*, *10*(2), e0117126. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0117126>
- Bainbridge, W. A., Isola, P., & Oliva, A. (2013). The intrinsic memorability of face photographs. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, *142*(4), 1323–1334. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0033872>
- Baron-Cohen, S., Wheelwright, S., Skinner, R., Martin, J., & Clubley, E. (2001). The autism-spectrum quotient (AQ): evidence from Asperger syndrome/high-functioning autism, males and females, scientists and mathematicians. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, *31*, 5–17.
- Blank, H., Alink, A., & Buchel, C. (2023). Multivariate functional neuroimaging analyses are represented in higher-level face-identity areas. *Communication Biology*, *6*(135). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-023-04508-8>
- Bruce, V., & Young, A. (1986). Understanding face recognition. *British Journal of Psychology*, *77*(3), 305–327. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8295.1986.tb02199.x>
- Chang, L., & Tsao, D. Y. (2017). The Code for Facial Identity in the Primate Brain. *Cell*, *169*(6), 1013–1028. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2017.05.011>
- Chen, X., Liu, X., Parker, B. J., Zhen, Z., & Weiner, K. S. (2023). Functionally and structurally distinct fusiform face area(s) in over 1000 participants. *NeuroImage*, *265*, 119765. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2022.119765>
- Collins, J. A., & Olson, I. R. (2014). Beyond the FFA: The role of the ventral anterior temporal lobes in face processing. *Neuropsychologia*, *61*(1), 65–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2014.06.005>
- Deen, B., Husain, G., & Freiwald, W. A. (2024). A familiar face and person processing area in the human temporal pole. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *121*, e2321346121. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2321346121>
- Desikan, R. S., Ségonne, F., Fischl, B., Quinn, B. T., Dickerson, B. C., Blacker, D., Buckner, R. L., Dale, A. M., Maguire, R. P., & Hyman, B. T. (2006). An automated labeling system for subdividing the human cerebral cortex on MRI scans into gyral based regions of interest. *NeuroImage*, *31*, 968–980.
- Devlin, J. T., Russell, R. P., Davis, M. H., Price, C. J., Wilson, J., Moss, H. E., Matthews, P. M., & Tyler, L. K. (2000). Susceptibility-induced loss of signal: Comparing PET and fMRI on a semantic task. *NeuroImage*, *11*(6 Pt 1), 589–600. <https://doi.org/10.1006/nimg.2000.0595>
- Duchaine, B., & Nakayama, K. (2006). The Cambridge Face Memory Test: results for neurologically intact individuals and an investigation of its validity using inverted face stimuli and prosopagnosic participants. *Neuropsychologia*, *44*(4), 576–585. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2005.07.001>
- Duchaine, B., & Yovel, G. (2015). A revised neural framework for face processing. *Annual Review of Vision Science*, *1*, 393–416. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-vision->

082114-035518

- Eickhoff, S. B., Stephan, K. E., Mohlberg, H., Grefkes, C., Fink, G. R., Amunts, K., & Zilles, K. (2005). A new SPM toolbox for combining probabilistic cytoarchitectonic maps and functional imaging data. *NeuroImage*, *25*(4), 1325–1335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2004.12.034>
- Elbich, D. B., & Scherf, K. S. (2017). Beyond the FFA: Brain-behavior correspondences in face recognition abilities. *NeuroImage*, *147*(June 2016), 409–422. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2016.12.042>
- Engell, A. D., & McCarthy, G. (2013). Probabilistic atlases for face and biological motion perception: An analysis of their reliability and overlap. *NeuroImage*, *74*, 140–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2013.02.025>
- Faul, F., Erdfelder, E., Lang, A.-G., & Buchner, A. (2007). G*Power 3: A flexible statistical power analysis program for the social, behavioral, and biomedical sciences. *Behavior Research Methods*, *39*(2), 175–191. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03193146>
- Foster, C., Bühlhoff, I., Bartels, A., & Zhao, M. (2021). Investigating holistic face processing within and outside of face-responsive brain regions. *NeuroImage*, *226*(April 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2020.117565>
- Freitag, C. M., Retz-Junginger, P., Retz, W., Seitz, C., Palmason, H., Meyer, J., Rösler, M., & Von Gontard, A. (2007). Evaluation der deutschen Version des Autismus-Spektrum-Quotienten (AQ) - Die kurzversion AQ-k. *Zeitschrift Fur Klinische Psychologie Und Psychotherapie*, *36*(4), 280–289. <https://doi.org/10.1026/1616-3443.36.4.280>
- Friston, K. J., Ashburner, J., Kiebel, S., Nichols, T., & Penny, W. (2007). Statistical parametric mapping: the analysis of functional brain images. In K. J. Friston, J. Ashburner, S. Kiebel, T. Nichols, & W. Penny (Eds.), *Academic Press*.
- Gainotti, G. (2013). Is the right anterior temporal variant of prosopagnosia a form of “associative prosopagnosia” or a form of “multimodal person recognition disorder”? *Neuropsychology Review*, *23*(2), 99–110. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11065-013-9232-7>
- Gainotti, G. (2018). The Anterior Temporal Lobes: New Frontiers Opened to Neuropsychological Research by Changes in Health Care and Disease Epidemiology. *The Journal of Neuropsychiatry and Clinical Neurosciences*, *30*(1), 22–30. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.neuropsych.17010002>
- Gainotti, G. (2025). Modality-Specific and Multimodal ‘Associative’ Forms of Face and Voice Recognition Disorders in Patients with Right Anterior Temporal Lesions: A Review of Single-Case Studies. *Brain Sciences*, *15*(12), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci15121309>
- Garlichs, A., & Blank, H. (2024). Prediction error processing and sharpening of expected information across the face- processing hierarchy. *Nature Communications*, *15*, 3407. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-47749-9>
- Gauthier, I., Skudlarski, P., Gore, J. C., & Anderson, A. W. (2000). Expertise for cars and birds recruits brain areas involved in face recognition. *Nature Neuroscience*, *3*(2),

191–197. <https://doi.org/10.1038/72140>

- Gauthier, I., Tarr, M. J., Anderson, A. W., Skudlarski, P., & Gore, J. C. (1999). Activation of the middle fusiform 'face area' increases with expertise in recognizing novel objects. *Nature Neuroscience*, *2*(6), 568–573.
- Gauthier, I., Tarr, M. J., Moylan, J., Skudlarski, P., Gore, J. C., & Anderson, A. W. (2000). The fusiform "face area" is part of a network that processes faces at the individual level. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, *12*(3), 495–504.
- Gobbini, M. I., & Haxby, J. V. (2007). Neural systems for recognition of familiar faces. *Neuropsychologia*, *45*(1), 32–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2006.04.015>
- Grill-Spector, K., Weiner, K. S., Kay, K., & Gomez, J. (2017). The Functional Neuroanatomy of Human Face Perception. *Annual Review of Vision Science*, *3*(1), 167–196. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-vision-102016-061214>
- Guntupalli, J. S., Wheeler, K. G., & Gobbini, M. I. (2017). Disentangling the Representation of Identity from Head View Along the Human Face Processing Pathway. *Cerebral Cortex*, *27*(1), 46–53. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhw344>
- Haist, F., Lee, K., & Stiles, J. (2010). Individuating faces and common objects produces equal responses in putative face-processing areas in the ventral occipitotemporal cortex. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, *4*(October), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2010.00181>
- Halai, A. D., Parkes, L. M., & Welbourne, S. R. (2015). Dual-echo fMRI can detect activations in inferior temporal lobe during intelligible speech comprehension. *NeuroImage*, *122*, 214–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2015.05.067>
- Halai, A. D., Welbourne, S. R., Embleton, K., & Parkes, L. M. (2014). A comparison of dual gradient-echo and spin-echo fMRI of the inferior temporal lobe. *Human Brain Mapping*, *35*(8), 4118–4128. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.22463>
- Haxby, J., Hoffman, E. A., & Gobbini, M. I. (2000). The distributed human neural system for face perception. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *4*(6), 223–233. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-6613\(00\)01482-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-6613(00)01482-0)
- Jonas, J., Rossion, B., Brissart, H., Frismand, S., Jacques, C., Hossu, G., Colnat-Coulbois, S., Vespignani, H., Vignal, J.-P., & Maillard, L. (2015). Beyond the core face-processing network: Intracerebral stimulation of a face-selective area in the right anterior fusiform gyrus elicits transient prosopagnosia. *Cortex*, *72*, 140–155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cortex.2015.05.026>
- Jonas, Jacques, Jacques, C., Liu-Shuang, J., Brissart, H., Colnat-Coulbois, S., Maillard, L., & Rossion, B. (2016). A face-selective ventral occipito-temporal map of the human brain with intracerebral potentials. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *113*(28), E4088–E4097. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1522033113>
- Kanwisher, N., McDermott, J., & Chun, M. M. (1997). The fusiform face area: A module in human extrastriate cortex specialized for face perception. *The Journal of*

- Neuroscience*, 17(11), 4302–4311. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.17-11-04302.1997>
- Kundu, P., Inati, S. J., Evans, J. W., Luh, W.-M., & Bandettini, P. A. (2012). Multiecho. *Neuroimage*, 60(3), 1759–1770. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2011.12.028>. Differentiating
- Kundu, Prantik, Voon, V., Balchandani, P., Lombardo, M. V., Poser, B. A., & Bandettini, P. A. (2017). Multi-echo fMRI: A review of applications in fMRI denoising and analysis of BOLD signals. *NeuroImage*, 154(March), 59–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2017.03.033>
- Lancaster, J. L., Tordesillas-Gutiérrez, D., Martinez, M., Salinas, F., Evans, A., Zilles, K., Mazziotta, J. C., & Fox, P. T. (2007). Bias between MNI and talairach coordinates analyzed using the ICBM-152 brain template. *Human Brain Mapping*, 28(11), 1194–1205. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.20345>
- Li, F.-F., Andreeto, M., Ranzato, M., & Perona, P. (2022). *Caltech 101 (1.0) [Data set]*. *CaltechDATA*. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.22002/D1.20086>
- Liu, J., Harris, A., & Kanwisher, N. (2010). Perception of Face Parts and Face Configurations: An fMRI Study. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, 22(1), 203–211. <https://doi.org/10.1162/jocn.2009.21203>
- Luzzi, S., Coccia, M., Polonara, G., Reverberi, C., Ceravolo, G., Silvestrini, M., Fringuelli, F., Baldinelli, S., Provinciali, L., & Gainotti, G. (2018). Selective associative phonagnosia after right anterior temporal stroke. *Neuropsychologia*, 31(116), 154–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2017.05.016>
- McGugin, Rankin W., Ryan, K. F., Tamber-Rosenau, B. J., & Gauthier, I. (2018). The Role of Experience in the Face-Selective Response in Right FFA. *Cerebral Cortex*, 28(6), 2071–2084. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhx113>
- McGugin, Rankin W., Sunday, M. A., & Gauthier, I. (2023). The neural correlates of domain-general visual ability. *Cerebral Cortex*, 33(8), 4280–4292. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhac342>
- McGugin, Rankin Williams, Van Gulick, A. E., Tamber-Rosenau, B. J., Ross, D. A., & Gauthier, I. (2015). Expertise effects in face-selective areas are robust to clutter and diverted attention, but not to competition. *Cerebral Cortex*, 25(9), 2610–2622. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhu060>
- McKone, E., Hall, A., Pidcock, M., Palermo, R., Wilkinson, R. B., Rivolta, D., Yovel, G., Davis, J. M., & O'Connor, K. B. (2011). Face ethnicity and measurement reliability affect face recognition performance in developmental prosopagnosia: evidence from the Cambridge Face Memory Test-Australian. *Cognitive Neuropsychology*, 28(2), 109–146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02643294.2011.616880>
- Moeller, S., Yacoub, E., Olman, C. A., Auerbach, E., Strupp, J., Harel, N., & Uğurbil, K. (2010). Multiband multislice GE-EPI at 7 tesla, with 16-fold acceleration using partial parallel imaging with application to high spatial and temporal whole-brain fMRI. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*, 63(5), 1144–1153.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.22361>

- Mugler, J. P. 3rd, & Brookeman, J. R. (1990). Three-dimensional magnetization-prepared rapid gradient-echo imaging (3D MP RAGE). *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*, *15*(1), 152–157. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/2374495>
- Nasr, S., & Tootell, R. B. H. (2012). Role of fusiform and anterior temporal cortical areas in facial recognition. *NeuroImage*, *63*(3), 1743–1753. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2012.08.031>
- O’Doherty, J., Kringelbach, M. L., Rolls, E. T., Hornak, J., & Andrews, C. (2001). Abstract reward and punishment representations in the human orbitofrontal cortex. *Nature Neuroscience*, *4*(1), 95–102.
- Oldfield, R. C. (1971). The assessment and analysis of handedness: The Edinburgh inventory. *Neuropsychologia*, *9*(1), 97–113. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0028-3932\(71\)90067-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0028-3932(71)90067-4)
- Pinsk, M.A., Arcaro, M., Weiner, K. S., Kalkus, J. F., Inati, S. J., Gross, C. G., & Kastner, S. (2009). Neural representations of faces and body parts in macaque and human cortex: a comparative fMRI study. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, *101*, 2581–2600.
- Pinsk, Mark A., Arcaro, M., Weiner, K. S., Kalkus, J. F., Inati, S. J., Gross, C. G., & Kastner, S. (2009). Neural representations of faces and body parts in macaque and human cortex: A comparative fMRI study. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, *101*(5), 2581–2600. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.91198.2008>
- Pitcher, D, Ianni, G., Holiday, K., & Ungerleider, L. G. (2023). Identifying the cortical face network with dynamic face stimuli: A large group fMRI study. *BioRxiv*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.09.26.559583>
- Pitcher, D, Walsh, V., & Duchaine, B. (2011). The role of the occipital face area in the cortical face perception network. *Experimental Brain Research*, *209*(4), 481–493. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00221-011-2579-1>
- Pitcher, David, Duchaine, B., Walsh, V., Yovel, G., & Kanwisher, N. (2011). The role of lateral occipital face and object areas in the face inversion effect. *Neuropsychologia*, *49*(12), 3448–3453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2011.08.020>
- Poltoratski, S., Kay, K., Finzi, D., & Grill-Spector, K. (2021). Holistic face recognition is an emergent phenomenon of spatial processing in face-selective regions. *Nature Communications*, *12*(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-24806-1>
- Poser, B. A., & Norris, D. G. (2009). Investigating the benefits of multi-echo EPI for fMRI at 7 T. *NeuroImage*, *45*(4), 1162–1172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2009.01.007>
- Poser, B. A., Versluis, M. J., Hoogduin, J. M., & Norris, D. G. (2006). BOLD contrast sensitivity enhancement and artifact reduction with multiecho EPI: Parallel-acquired inhomogeneity-desensitized fMRI. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*, *55*(6), 1227–1235. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.20900>
- Project, H. B. (2024). *EBRAINS Human Brain Atlas*. Retrieved October 15, 2025, from

<https://ebrains.e>

- Rajimehr, R., Young, J. C., & Tootell, R. B. H. (2009). An anterior temporal face patch in human cortex, predicted by macaque maps. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *106*(6), 1995–2000.
- Rossion, B. (2008). Constraining the cortical face network by neuroimaging studies of acquired prosopagnosia. *NeuroImage*, *40*, 423–426.
- Rossion, B. (2014). Understanding face perception by means of prosopagnosia and neuroimaging. *Frontiers in Bioscience*, *6*, 258–307.
- Rossion, B, Schiltz, C., Robaye, L., Pirenne, D., & Crommelinck, M. (2001). How does the brain discriminate familiar and unfamiliar faces?: a PET study of face categorical perception. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, *13*(7), 1019–1034.
<https://doi.org/10.1162/089892901753165917>
- Rossion, Bruno, Hanseeuw, B., & Dricot, L. (2012). Defining face perception areas in the human brain: A large-scale factorial fMRI face localizer analysis. *Brain and Cognition*, *79*(2), 138–157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bandc.2012.01.001>
- Rossion, Bruno, Jacques, C., & Jonas, J. (2024). The anterior fusiform gyrus: the ghost in the cortical face machine. *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2024.105535>
- Schrouff, J., Raccach, O., Baek, S., Rangarajan, V., Salehi, S., Mourão-Miranda, J., Helili, Z., Daitch, A. L., & Parvizi, J. (2020). Fast temporal dynamics and causal relevance of face processing in the human temporal cortex. *Nature Communications*, *11*(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-14432-8>
- Shah, P., Gaule, A., Sowden, S., Bird, G., & Cook, R. (2015). The 20-item prosopagnosia index (PI20): a self-report instrument for identifying developmental prosopagnosia. *Royal Society Open Science*, *2*, 140343.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.140343>
- Smith, S. M., Jenkinson, M., Woolrich, M. W., Beckmann, C. F., Behrens, T. E., Johansen-Berg, H., Bannister, P. R., De Luca, M., Drobnjak, I., Flitney, D. E., Niazy, R. K., Saunders, J., Vickers, J., Zhang, Y., De Stefano, N., Brady, J. M., & Matthews, P. M. (2004). Advances in functional and structural MR image analysis and implementation as FSL. *NeuroImage*, *23 Suppl 1*, S208-19.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2004.07.051>
- Tsao, D. Y., Freiwald, W. A., Tootell, R. B. H., & Livingstone, M. S. (2006). A cortical region consisting entirely of face-selective cells. *Science*, *311*(5761), 670–674.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1119983.A>
- Tsao, D. Y., Moeller, S., & Freiwald, W. A. (2008). Comparing face patch systems in macaques and humans. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *105*, 19514–19519.
- Turner, R., & Geyer, S. (2014). Comparing like with like: the power of knowing where you are. *Brain Connectivity*, *4*(7), 547–557.
<https://doi.org/10.1089/brain.2014.0261>

- Valentine, T. (1991). A unified account of the effects of distinctiveness, inversion, and race in face recognition. *The Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology Section A: Human Experimental Psychology*, *43*(2), 161–204.
- Veale, J. F. (2014). Edinburgh Handedness Inventory - Short Form: A revised version based on confirmatory factor analysis. *Laterality*, *19*(2), 164–177.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1357650X.2013.783045>
- Volfart, A., Yan, X., Maillard, L., Colnat-Coulbois, S., Hossu, G., Rossion, B., & Jonas, J. (2022). Intracerebral electrical stimulation of the right anterior fusiform gyrus impairs human face identity recognition. *NeuroImage*, *250*, 118932.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2022.118932>
- Weiner, K. S., & Grill-Spector, K. (2010). Sparsely-distributed organization of face and limb activations in human ventral temporal cortex. *NeuroImage*, *52*(4), 1559–1573.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2010.04.262>
- Weiner, K. S., & Grill-Spector, K. (2012). The improbable simplicity of the fusiform face area. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *16*(5), 251–254.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2012.03.003>
- Weiner, K. S., & Grill-Spector, K. (2013). Neural representations of faces and limbs neighbor in human high-level visual cortex: Evidence for a new organization principle. *Psychological Research*, *77*(1), 74–97. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00426-011-0392-x>
- Wilmer, J. B., Germine, L., Chabris, C. F., Chatterjee, G., Williams, M., Loken, E., Nakayama, K., & Duchaine, B. (2010). Human face recognition ability is specific and highly heritable. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *107*(11), 5238–5241.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0913053107>
- Yang, H., Susilo, T., & Duchaine, B. (2016). The anterior temporal face area contains invariant representations of face identity that can persist despite the loss of right FFA and OFA. *Cerebral Cortex*, *26*, 1096–1107.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhu289>
- Yovel, G., Wilmer, J. B., & Duchaine, B. (2014). What can individual differences reveal about face processing? *Front Hum Neurosci*, *8*, 562.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2014.00562>
- Zhen, Z., Yang, Z., Huang, L., Kong, X. zhen, Wang, X., Dang, X., Huang, Y., Song, Y., & Liu, J. (2015). Quantifying interindividual variability and asymmetry of face-selective regions: A probabilistic functional atlas. *NeuroImage*, *113*, 13–25.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2015.03.010>

Supplements

Dual-echo EPI sequence pilot: the ventral anterior temporal lobe

tSNR maps

Before the main data collection, we piloted the dual-echo EPI sequence with two participants (not included in the main task analysis) to examine if it was appropriate for imaging problematic anterior regions. For this pilot, tSNR maps were generated based on functional images for one run of the face area localiser (Axelrod & Yovel, 2013) acquired with the dual-echo EPI sequence (see 'Image Acquisition, Functional MRI' main manuscript for parameters). We also generated tSNR maps, again based on one run of the face area localiser, for a standard single-echo EPI sequence used commonly at the neuroimaging centre (TE = 25 ms; flip angle = 80 degrees; TR = 2.36 s; GRAPPA acceleration factor = 2; 48 slices whole brain coverage; 2.5 mm slice thickness; in plane resolution 3 mm x 3 mm; bandwidth = 2232 Hz/pixel). The data for both sequences were acquired in the same imaging session, alongside a T1-weighted three-dimensional MP-RAGE image (parameters as per 'Structural MRI' section, main manuscript), for each participant. The dual-echo tSNR maps were generated based on the hybrid time series (see 'Echo-combination and pre-processing' main manuscript) obtained after the application of a high-pass filter with a cut-off period of $10 \times TR$. Similarly, the single-echo tSNR maps were generated from the motion-corrected and high-pass filtered time series. Further pre-processing included co-registration, segmentation, and normalisation to MNI standard stereotactic space using the forward deformation field outputted from the segmentation process. The spatially normalised tSNR maps were written to the same isotropic resolution of 3mm^3 . To characterise signal properties in the ventral anterior temporal lobe, average tSNR values were extracted (using FSL stats) for both sequence maps for the anterior divisions of the temporal fusiform cortex and the inferior temporal gyrus defined based on probabilistic maps of the respective regions from the Harvard-Oxford Cortical Structural Atlas (Desikan et al., 2006), implemented in FSL (Smith et al., 2004), thresholded at 30%. At this threshold there was minimal anatomical overlap between the regions facilitating discrete tSNR value extraction per region (Figure S1B). The tSNR values were used to characterise the signal in the dual-echo EPI, rather than a direct controlled comparison with the SE-EPI sequence. However, the average tSNR values were divided by the square root of the TR of the respective sequence to take into account differences in temporal sampling between sequences.

tSNR characteristics: the ventral anterior temporal lobe

For the two pilot participants, there was a pattern for higher tSNR values in the temporal fusiform cortex, anterior division for the dual-echo (TR-normalised tSNR = 38.76, participant 1; TR-normalised tSNR = 32.10, participant 2), than the single-echo (TR-normalised tSNR = 20.41, participant 1; TR-normalised tSNR = 15.01, participant 2) fMRI sequence (Figure S1). This pattern also emerged for the inferior temporal gyrus, anterior division (dual-echo: TR-normalised tSNR = 54.16, participant 1; TR-normalised tSNR =

53.14, participant 2; single-echo: TR-normalised tSNR = 23.47, participant 1; TR-normalised tSNR = 21.05, participant 2). This demonstrated the feasibility of the dual-echo EPI sequence for examining BOLD responses in these problematic regions.

Figure S1. (A) Mean TR-normalised temporal signal-to-noise (tSNR) values for the standard single-echo and dual-echo fMRI sequence for the ventral anterior temporal lobe for two participants. Values are shown separately for the anterior inferior temporal gyrus (ant ITG, cyan colour) and the anterior temporal fusiform cortex (ant TFC, blue colour). Black dots denote individual participant values. (B) Anatomical maps of the ant ITG (cyan colour) and ant TFC (blue colour) used to spatially define the brain regions from which the mean tSNR values were extracted. The maps are displayed on a standard MNI 152 brain template.

Ventral core-face system mask

Figure S2. Visualisation of the ventral core-face system mask (blue) used in the functional MRI analyses, displayed on the MNI template brain in sagittal view (left of figure; right hemisphere) and coronal view (right of figure). The combined mask, restricted to grey matter voxels, included the bilateral inferior division of the lateral occipital cortex, occipital fusiform gyrus, temporal occipital fusiform cortex, temporal

fusiform cortex posterior division, and anterior divisions of the temporal fusiform cortex and inferior temporal gyrus.

Functional MRI Results

Whole-brain analyses: Faces > watches (both runs combined)

At the whole brain level ($p < 0.05$ FWE corrected), face-selective responses were evident in the temporal occipital fusiform cortex, corresponding to FFA-1 and FFA-2 (Table S1). Face-selective responses were also observed in regions often categorised as part of the ‘extended system’ for face processing (Haxby et al., 2000). Particularly evident were bilateral responses in the amygdala, as well as the lateralised responses in the hippocampus and frontal regions (Table S1).

Table S1. Overview of the face-selective responses for the whole brain analysis for the contrast ‘faces > watches’ for both runs combined.

Faces > watches (combined runs)												
	Right hemisphere						Left Hemisphere					
	x	y	z	T	Z	Size (mm ³)	x	y	z	T	Z	Size (mm ³)
p < 0.05 (FWE corrected, whole brain)												
FFA-1 (TOFC)	43	-50	-22	6.85	5.37	475						
FFA-2 (TOFC)	43	-42	-26	8.78	6.26							
Amygdala	21	-10	-16	9.85	6.68	725	-20	-7	-16	8.64	6.20	550
	28	1	-24	9.24	6.45	138						
Hippocampus	21	-25	-12	6.87	5.38	100						
Frontal pole	36	36	-14	6.17	4.99	25						
Frontal medial cortex							-10	48	-16	6.33	5.08	38
p < 0.001 (uncorrected, whole brain)												
FFA-1 (TOFC)*	43	-50	-22	6.85	5.37	2588	-42	-42	-22	4.74	4.11	850
FFA-2 (TOFC)*	43	-42	-26	8.78	6.26		-42	-55	-22	3.84	3.47	
aFG (post. TFC/ITG)	43	-30	-16	4.48	3.93		-45	-35	-18	3.85	3.47	
post. TFC/ITG	46	-15	-30	3.61	3.29	25						
aTL-FA (ant. TFC)	31	-5	-36	3.84	3.46	63						
LOC	56	-65	18	5.56	4.64	1963	-55	-65	28	5.33	4.50	963

46	-60	24	4.89	4.21	-52	-70	22	4.93	4.23
53	-67	26	4.41	3.88	-52	-72	14	4.52	3.96

Results at $p < 0.05$ (FWE corrected, whole brain) include all brain responses identified i.e., core-face and extended system responses. Results at $p < 0.001$ (uncorrected, whole brain) are reported for core-face system responses only. *FFA-1 and FFA-2 (right hemisphere) responses are evident at $p < 0.05$ but also reported here at $p < 0.001$ as they form part of the cluster that revealed the third face-selective peak ($y = -30$) at this threshold. FFA = fusiform face area; aFG = anterior fusiform gyrus; aTL-FA = anterior temporal lobe face area; post. = posterior; ant. = anterior; TOFC = Temporal occipital fusiform cortex; TFC = Temporal fusiform cortex; ITG = Inferior temporal gyrus; LOC = lateral occipital cortex.

Ventral core-face mask: Faces > baseline (both runs combined)

Table S2. Overview of the responses for the ventral core-face mask analysis for the contrast ‘faces > baseline’ for both runs combined.

Faces > baseline (combined runs)												
Right hemisphere							Left Hemisphere					
	x	y	z	T	Z	Size (mm ³)	x	y	z	T	Z	Size (mm ³)
p < 0.05 (FWE corrected)												
LOC	38	-75	-16	11.53	7.25	17863	-47	-77	2	5.91	4.85	100
TOFC	41	-40	-22	10.32	6.85							
OFG	43	-65	-18	11.13	7.12		-42	-67	-20	11.65	7.29	13650
							-30	-80	-16	11.21	7.15	
							-20	-82	-16	9.74	6.64	
ant. TFC	28	-5	-36	7.97	5.91	213						

LOC = lateral occipital cortex; TOFC = Temporal occipital fusiform cortex; OFG = occipital fusiform gyrus; TFC = Temporal fusiform cortex; ant = anterior. The anatomical labels assigned to the reported co-ordinates were based on the anatomical maps created from the Harvard-Oxford Cortical Structural Atlas. See the main text (‘Statistical Inference’) for full details on anatomical map creation and peak co-ordinate anatomical labelling.

Figure S3. Responses for the contrast faces > baseline. Non-face-selective responses in the core-face

system (displayed at t threshold = 5.30). Crosshairs indicate the peak voxel location in the inferior division of the lateral occipital cortex shown at $x = 38$, $y = -75$, $z = -16$ in sagittal (left) and coronal (right) view in the right hemisphere. This peak aligns with the expected functional location of the OFA in the right hemisphere. Responses are overlaid on a mean structural MNI152 T1 weighted image. The colour bar represents t values.